

	Form	Fee	Cheque Payable to
BC Children's Hospital			
Through PHSA	BCCH - FOI Request Form	No fee	
Alberta Children's Hospital & Stollery Children's Hospital (Alberta Health Services)			
Through AHS	AHS - FOI Request Form	\$25	Alberta Health Services
Jim Pattison Children's Hospital (Saskatchewan Health Authority)			
	SHA - FOI Request Form	\$20	Saskatchewan Health Au
Children's Hospital of Manitoba			
	CHM - FOI Request Form	No fee	
Hospital for Sick Children			
	SK - FOI Request Form	\$5	Hospital for Sick Childre
Children's Hospital of Eastern Ontario			
	CHEO - FOI Request Form	\$5	Children's Hospital of Ea
McMaster Children's Hospital (Hamilton Health Sciences)			
	MCH - FOI Request Form	\$5	Hamilton Health Science

Children's Hospital (London Health Sciences Centre)

LHSC - FOI Request Form

\$5 London Health Sciences

Montreal Children's Hospital

QU - FOI Request Form

No fee

CHU Sainte-Justine

QU - FOI Request Form

No fee

IWK Health Centre

IWK - FOI Request Form

\$5 IWK Health Centre

Janeway Children's Hospital

Through EHA

JCH - FOI Request Form

No fee

Total Fees:

\$130

Mail Address	Contact	Link
Senior Director, Information Access & Privacy Services 200 - 1333 West Broadway Vancouver, BC V6H 4C1	privacyandfoi@phsa.ca	http://www.phsa.ca/about/access
Alberta Health Services, Information & Privacy 5th floor, North Tower, Seventh Street Plaza 10030 - 107 Street Edmonton, AB T5J 3E4	privacy@ahs.ca	https://www.albertahealthservices.ca
Attn: Michael McGill Saskatoon City Hospital Room 3800 - 701 Queen Street Saskatoon, SK S7K 0M7	306-655-7549 306 514 7972 during covid	https://www.saskhealthauthorities.ca
HSC Winnipeg - Health Information Services Attn: Health Information Correspondence MS137 - 820 Sherbrook Street Winnipeg, MB R3A 1R9 OR Winnipeg Regional Health Authority 4th floor - 650 Main Street Winnipeg, MB R3B 1E2	fippa@gov.mb.ca	https://www.gov.mb.ca/fippa/
Freedom of Information Office The Hospital for Sick Children 555 University Avenue Toronto, ON M5G 1X8	416-813-7654 x 228014	http://www.sickkids.ca/AboutUs
Attn: Freedom of Information Coordinator Children's Hospital of Eastern Ontario 401 Smyth Road Ottawa, ON K1H 8L1	N/A	https://www.cheo.on.ca/en/about
Privacy and Freedom of Information Office Hamilton Health Sciences 100 King Street West PO Box 2000	N/A	https://www.hamiltonhealthsciences.ca

Hamilton, ON L8N 3Z5

Privacy Office 519-685-8500 x 32996 <https://www.lhsc.on.ca/accou>
800 Commissioners Road East
PO Box 5010, STN B
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Esther Briand esther.briand@muhc.r <https://www.cai.gouv.qc.ca/er>
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Dossiers usagers et medicaux
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Privacy Coordinator privacy@iwk.nshealth.c <http://www.iwk.nshealth.ca/pe>
IWK Health Centre
5850/5980 University Avenue
PO Box 9700
Halifax, NS B3K 6R8

Attn: Brian Taylor, ATIPP Coordinator brian.taylor@easternhe <https://www.gov.nl.ca/atipp/fil>
Information Security and Privacy Office
Eastern Health Authority
760 Topsail Road
Mount Pearl, NL A1N 3J5

Mailed	Letter of Acknowledg	Response
Mailed Feb 28	Received Mar 18	Responded Apr 14

Mailed Feb 28	Received Mar	Responded Mar 27
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Mailed Mar 3		
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Mailed Feb 28	Received Mar 13	Responded Apr 14
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Mailed Mar 3	Received Jul 17	Responded Jul 22
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Mailed Feb 28	Received Mar 30	Responded Jul 13
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Mailed Mar 3		Responded Aug 12
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Mailed Mar 3 Received Mar 27 Responded Apr 3

Mailed Feb 28 Responded Jun 13

Mailed Feb 28 Responded May 21

Mailed Mar 3 Responded May 27

Mailed Feb 28 Received Mar 17 28th Oct

Results

Follow-Up

No records; has a month C&W meeting; follows DSD Guidelines & Chicago Consensus

No policy documents

follow up (call) Jun 10, 18th and 27th August

No records exist

No records located

Follow-up email Jun 12

No records exist, no written guidelines or protocols

Follow-up email Jun 9; responded Jun 12, is curr

No specific policies/guidelines exist; uses standards & cc Follow-up email Jun 9; responded Jun 9, did not
- Uses CPSO & Am. Urological Assoc. standards
- Clinical services adhere to: 1) the World Professional Association for Transgender Health (WPATH) guide
- Ped. endocrinologists follow: 1) Consensus statement on management of intersex disorders, 2) Global E

- Many physicians align with SPU Intersex Task Force and SPU Leadership joint policy statements, and Per

No records

No protocols exist

Follow-up email Jun 9; responded Jun 10, being t

No documents, case-by-case response

No written policies; follows published clinical guidelines Follow up email May 27, asking for these guideli

No writtent policies etc.

Follow-up email Jun 9; responded Jun 9, extende

